

Table 2. RTV-infected hills at different days after transplanting (DT).

Time of observation (DT)	RTV-infected hills (no.)			
	TN1		IR36	
	With azolla	Without azolla	With azolla	Without azolla
15	4.6	6.2	0	0
30	65.6	63.4	0.4	1.0
45	83.6	84.2	2.0	1.8

days after transplanting (DT). TN1 showed more than 80% infection 45 DT but IR36 remained almost disease free in both treatments (Table 2).

Results obtained in the greenhouse and in the field trial show that azolla application does not cause higher RTV incidence or render the resistant variety susceptible to RTV. □

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Biochemical properties of discolored rice grains

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The biochemical properties of discolored rice grains were analyzed and compared with those of healthy white grains (see table). Freshly harvested rice was dehusked and discolored grains were classified as brown, purple, or green. Associated fungi were isolated by blotter technique. Brown and purple grains yielded three species of fungi: *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, and *Curvularia lunata*. Green grains had *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

Brown grains had higher levels of phenol, reducing and nonreducing sugars, amylose, and gel consistency than white grains. Gelatinization score was lower than for normal grains. Brown grains contained glycine in addition to the eight other amino acids present in white grains.

Purple grains also had high levels of

Biochemical properties of discolored rice grains.

Property	Brown grain	Purple grain	Green grain	White (healthy)
Phenolic content (µg/g fresh wt)	260	56	65	50
Reducing sugar (µg/g fresh wt)	350	430	320	190
Nonreducing sugar (µg/g fresh wt)	1000	960	880	820
Percent amylose	9.4	8.0	7.6	8.8
Amino acids				
Isoleucine	+	+	+	+
Tryptophan	+	+	+	+
Tyrosine	+	+	+	+
Alanine	+	-	+	+
Aspartic acid	+	+	+	+
Glycine	+	+	+	-
Arginine	+	+	+	+
Histidine	+	+	+	+
Cystine	+	+	+	+
Gel consistency (mm)	147	123	96	119
Gelatinization	Intermediate	High or intermediate	High	low

phenol, reducing and nonreducing sugars, and gel consistency. Percent amylose and gelatinization were less than for healthy grains. Alanine, present in white grains, was not detectable, but purple grains,

contained glycine. Results for green grains were similar to those for brown grains, but brown grains contained more amylose and had higher gel consistency than other colored grains. □

Rice grain discoloration

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Rice grain discoloration reduces market value and consumption appeal and often is associated with pathogens. Pathogens that cause grain discoloration and the relationship between discoloration and weather factors were studied in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Seeds collected from mature panicles were dehusked and the discolored grains were classified as green, purple, or brown. Associated fungi were isolated by the blotter technique using 5,000 grains of

each calor. White grains (control) yielded no fungi. Green grains (0.8%) yielded *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Among the purple grains, 54.0% yielded *H. oryzae*, 12% yielded *Trichoconis padwickii*, and 5.0% yielded *Curvularia lunata*. Brown grains yielded 65.0, 8.0, and 3.0%, res-

pectively, of these fungi.

Panicles at the various stages of development in the field were inoculated by spraying a spore suspension (40,000 cells/ml) of the 3 species of fungi. Control plants were sprayed with water. The panicles were covered with paper bags im-

Table 1. Percentage of grains infected by the fungi.

Fungus species	Infected grains (%)			
	Flower	Milk	Soft dough	Dough
<i>H. oryzae</i>	26.5	21.5	5.9	0
<i>T. padwickii</i>	22.4	19.5	1.9	0
<i>C. lunata</i>	23.2	20.6	1.8	0
Control (water spray)	5.4	0	0	0

mediately after spraying and kept covered until maturity.

Percentages of discolored grains are given in Table 1. All three species of fungi caused discoloration when inoculated at flower, milk, and soft dough stages. *H. oryzae* caused maximum discoloration. Inoculation at flower stage caused more

discoloration than at milk stage or soft dough stage. Inoculation at dough stage produced no discoloration.

The influence of weather factors on grain discoloration in commonly grown rice varieties maturing at different months was studied throughout the year (Table 2). Panicles of the crops harvested from

October to December had more discolored grains. Low temperature, high humidity, high rainfall, and more rainy days prevailed during these months and appear to cause a higher percent of discoloration. Temperature range at flowering stage seemed to have more influence on the high incidence of grain discoloration.

Table 2. Grain discoloration in relation to weather factors.

Month	Temperature (°C)		Relative humidity (%)	Rainfall		Discolored grains (%)									
	Max	Min		mm	Rainy days (no.)	CO 39	Ponni	Bhavarii	IR8	IR20	Vaigai	TNI	Kannagi	Benni Bhog ^a	CO 13 ^b
Jun 1980	31.2	23.0	78	30.3	6	5	4	9	1	4	2	3	8	14	6
Jul	30.9	22.5	81	25.7	3	5	5	9	2	5	3	3	8	14	6
Aug	31.1	22.1	79	15.7	2	6	6	9	2	5	3	3	8	14	6
Sep	32.0	21.4	87	67.9	3	29	31	39	6	22	29	32	38	29	32
Oct	30.9	21.3	90	217.9	8	55	42	56	16	35	62	60	72	72	55
Nov	29.4	20.3	90	176.7	8	52	41	54	15	33	61	60	71	71	51
Dec	29.6	19.0	88	6.8	1	73	82	80	72	76	72	88	80	83	61
Jan 1981	30.1	18.1	87	0.2	1	32	33	29	12	30	33	33	30	43	31
Feb	32.6	17.0	77	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	0
Mar	34.3	20.8	83	21.4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

^a Susceptible check for *H. oryzae*. ^b Local check for blast.

Accumulation of phenolics in rice varieties due to infection by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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Phenolic compounds play a vital role in the defense mechanism of plants against infectious agents. The participation of phenolic compounds in bacterial leaf blight disease resistance was studied.

Rice varieties ASDS (moderately susceptible), CO 40 (susceptible), TNI

(highly susceptible), and TNAU7 124 (moderately resistant) were sown in pots and fertilized with 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha. Seedlings were clip inoculated with freshly isolated bacterial suspension 10⁸ cells/ml 15 days after seeding. Samples of leaves from the inoculated plants

Table 1. Effect of *X. oryzae* infection on total phenolics and ortho-dihydroxy phenols in rice varieties^a

Variety	Plant stage ^b	Total content (µg/g leaf tissue) of											
		Phenol						Ortho-dihydroxy phenol					
		7 DI		10 DI		15 DI		7 DI		10 DI		15 DI	
		H	D	H	D	H	D	H	D	H	D	H	D
TNAU7124	S	2.67	3.30	2.51	2.84	2.51	2.62	1.65	1.87	1.91	2.25	2.42	2.31
	T	2.33	2.56	2.04	2.26	1.84	2.04	0.96	1.62	1.06	1.84	1.66	1.93
	B	2.51	2.92	2.25	2.53	2.12	2.34	0.74	1.46	0.72	0.73	0.46	0.60
ASD5	S	2.52	2.80	2.26	2.19	2.19	2.37	1.91	2.21	2.09	1.75	2.09	2.08
	T	2.51	2.54	2.23	2.31	2.18	2.15	1.18	1.98	1.52	1.98	1.36	1.59
	B	2.64	2.66	2.47	2.45	2.34	1.84	1.87	1.45	0.72	1.04	0.56	1.43
TNI	S	2.53	2.61	2.52	2.95	2.03	2.28	1.65	1.32	1.54	1.78	2.45	2.09
	T	2.33	1.97	2.30	1.90	2.11	2.29	1.55	1.73	1.26	1.36	1.15	1.56
	B	2.46	2.52	2.68	2.89	2.34	2.21	1.54	1.50	0.60	0.73	0.61	0.98
CO 40	S	2.64	2.85	2.83	2.64	2.49	2.24	1.43	1.80	2.14	2.21	2.14	2.21
	T	2.43	2.63	2.26	2.36	1.93	1.99	1.34	1.60	1.47	1.50	0.97	1.52
	B	2.29	2.32	2.34	2.46	2.10	2.24	1.50	1.54	2.04	2.06	0.98	0.61

^a DI = days after inoculation, H = healthy, D = diseased. ^b S = seedling, T = tillering, B = boot leaf.

Conclusion

	CD
Variety	0.083
*Stage	0.072
*Sampling time	0.072
*Inoculation	0.059
	S ₁ S ₂ S ₃
	T ₁ T ₂ T ₃
	I ₂ I ₁